

Discrete potential fluids in the supercritical region.

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Supercritical fluids are an interesting area of research because their use in industrial processes has environmental benefits. Since their processes are low energy consumption they are considered as green solvents of the future. However, the study of the supercritical region remains a controversial issue, particularly, the possibility to find three different regime: gas-like, liquid-like and a mixture of them. The existence of a line (Widom line) or a region (delta Widom) that delimit this behavior is still under discussion. In this work we assume that this border is a line, like a continuation of a vapor-liquid saturation curve in the pressure-temperature plane. The Widom line is defined by the locus of points of maximum correlation length. Taking advantage of the relation that exists between the correlation length with the response functions and scalar curvature in the vicinity of the critical point, we build the Widom line with the locus of extrema of response functions and scalar curvature, and use the coincidence of these curves to determine the end of the Widom line. The Widom lines for Square-Well of variable range and Hard-Core Lennard-Jones systems are obtained using analytical equations of state. We propose a quantitative criterion to determine the end of this line. Besides, we give a new and alternative way of determining this line using the locus of the pressure inflection points (obtained in the density-pressure plane) and look for the coincidence of these points with the locus of the maxima of the isothermal compressibility in the temperature-pressure plane.

I. INTRODUCTION

Supercritical fluids are an important research topic because they have a great variety of industrial applications that are sustainable, environmentally friendly and cost efficient.[1]

One of the open questions about this region is the possibility to find three different regimes: gas-like, liquid-like, and a mixture of them. [2–6] The existence of a line dividing the gas-like and liquid like regimes was first observed for argon by Jones and Walker,[2] defined as an extrapolation of the vapor-liquid saturation curve in the pressure-temperature plane. This idea was also employed by Griffiths and Wheeler in their famous work on critical points of multi component systems,[7] and also by Anisimov *et al.* in their work on the thermodynamics of fluid polyamorphism.[8] Jones and Walker noticed that in this extrapolated line close to the critical point the maxima of the isobaric heat capacity was also located. Later, this border line was redefined by Xu *et al.*[9] as the locus of maximum correlation length in the supercritical region, the so called "Widom line". Since the correlation length, ξ , is not easy to obtain, most authors interested in determining either the Widom line or searching for a critical point, instead of directly calculating the correlation length, took profit of the relation that exists *close enough* to the critical point and the response functions, as for instance, the isothermal compressibility, β_T , ($\beta_T \sim \xi^{2-\eta}$), where η is a critical exponent,[10–19] and/or the curvature scalar, R , ($R \sim |\xi^3|$). [15, 20–22] The dynamical properties, such as, viscosity, diffusion

coefficient, sound dispersion have also been used to detect this crossover, called Frenkel line.[16, 23] Besides, changes on the behavior of the structural properties, such as the pair correlation function or the cluster formation in hydrogen-bonded substances,[6, 24, 25] have been used to detect a percolation transition. The existence of a Widom Line or a Delta Widom region is also under discussion, especially when analyzing this region with simulation and data science approaches.[26–29]

Concerning the Widom line, defined in terms of the maxima of the response functions, Schienbein and Marx[27] and Strong *et al.*[5] have recently reviewed previous works and they pointed out that there are two main problems on its definition. Different results are obtained depending on the selection of the response function and/or the type of thermodynamic path (isobars or isotherms) followed. The determination of the Widom line based on the analysis of maxima of response functions or curvature scalar has been done for some simple systems with either a given analytical equations of state (EOS) or using a given potential in simulation studies. Among the works that have used theoretical EOS to determine it, one can mention: Ruppeiner *et al.*,[15] Brazhkin and Rhyzhov,[14] May and Mausbach [21] using van der Waals (vdW) EOS and two Lennard-Jones (LJ) EOS (a modified version of the Benedict-Webb-Rubin[30] (MBWR) and the Kolafa and Nezbeda[31] equations), and Brazhkin *et al.*[12] using a Square-well (SW) EOS.[13] For real systems, like water, one can mention the works of Schienbein [27] who used the IAPWS95 empirical analytic EOS and the work of Corradini *et al.* who used atomistic models (TIP4P,

TIP4P/2005, SPC/E, TIP5P, and TIP3P) with simulation studies, [17, 27] and for other substances using empirical EOS for argon, nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide, water, and for some mixtures.[19, 32–35]

Although it seems that the Widom line or Widom Delta have already been obtained for some "toy" potentials fluid models (SW, vdW, LJ, Yukawa) there still are open questions. For instance, Brazhkhin *et al.*[13] studied a SW system using a solution of the Ornstein-Zernike, under the Percus-Yevick closure, that enabled them to get analytic expressions for the correlation length ξ and a simple SW EOS. They checked if the maxima of R and the maxima of some response functions coincided and defined a Widom line in the neighbourhood of the critical point. They found that the locus of the extrema do not coincide, at least for the SW case for $\lambda = 1.35$ and they suggested to use instead the Frenkel line definition in terms of dynamic properties. Since this is the only published work devoted to the SW systems, it deserves some attention; for instance we can investigate if the same conclusion is obtained using other SW EOS and/or other SW ranges, or other hard-core discrete potentials.

In this work we present some results for the Widom line for some discrete potentials: a SW of variable range and Hard-Core Lennard-Jones (HCLJ) with analytic expressions for their EOS.

The locus of maximum correlation length was estimated using two routes:

- Thermodynamic curvature method developed by Ruppeiner *et al.*[15]
- The method based on locating the maxima of some response functions.

For this study, we assumed that the Widom line is the locus of maximum correlation length in the thermodynamic temperature-pressure plane; as a continuation of the vapor-liquid coexistence curve in that plane. Besides, this line starts in the critical point and ends where the extrema of the response functions and the curvature scalar no longer coincide. For the SW potential we will use available analytical EOS accordingly with its range. For the HCLJ we will use the analytical equation of state (EOS) obtained using the Discrete Perturbation Theory (DPT).[36, 37] This theory is a generator of equations of state for a great variety of potentials: continuous and discontinuous. Its main advantage is that it provides an analytical expression for the Helmholtz free energy as a high temperature perturbation expansion explicit in density, temperature and the parameters that characterize the interaction potentials.

This work is presented as follows: In section II we describe the SW and HCLJ Helmholtz free-energy high temperature expansions and their related thermodynamics properties. In section III the methodology to obtain the Widom line is discussed. Results are presented

in section IV. Finally in section V we give the main conclusions of this work.

II. DISCRETE POTENTIAL EQUATIONS OF STATE

A. Square well potential

For the SW potential of variable range, λ , we will use the analytical equations of Pavlyukhin[38] for intermediate ranges ($\lambda < 2.5$), and Benavides and del Río[39] for longer ranges. These EOS were obtained by combining Perturbation theory and Simulation data. In both cases, for a fluid system made of N spheres of diameter, σ , inside a volume, V , at a temperature, T , the excess reduced Helmholtz free-energy, $a^{ex} \equiv \frac{A^{ex}}{Nk_B T}$, is expressed as:

$$a_{SW}^{ex}(\rho^*, T^*, \lambda) \equiv a_{HS}(\rho^*) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_i(\rho^*, \lambda)}{T^{*i}}. \quad (1)$$

In this equation, the reduced density is $\rho^* = \rho\sigma^3$ and the reduced temperatures is $T^* = k_B T/\epsilon$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant. For the reference potential, that in this case is the hard-sphere system, we will use the Carnahan-Starling equation of state:[40]

$$a_{HS}(\rho^*) = \frac{4\eta - 3\eta^2}{(1 - \eta^2)}, \quad (2)$$

with $\eta = \frac{\pi}{6}\rho^*$, being the hard-sphere packing fraction. The $a_i(\rho^*, \lambda)$ terms can be taken from the corresponding EOS in the original references of Pavlyukhin,[38] up to fourth-order, and Benavides and del Río,[39] up to second-order.

B. Hard-Core Lennard-Jones potential

The mathematical expression for the HCLJ potential is the following:

$$\phi_{HCLJ}(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } x \leq 1 \\ 4\epsilon_{LJ} \left[\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^6 \right] & \text{if } x > 1, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $x = r/\sigma_{LJ}$.

The discrete version of this potential can be constructed choosing the length of the discretization interval, $I = (\lambda_c - \lambda_0)$, with $\lambda_0 = 1$ being the reduced potential contact value and $\lambda_c = 13$ being the reduced LJ cutoff distance selected. So, for a discrete LJ potential $I = 12$. The partition width of the interval I was selected as $w = 0.07$. The number of discretizations for a fixed width selection is determined with the above parameters,

$n = \text{rint}[I/w]$, with rint being the nearest integer number. Thus, for the LJ potential, $n = 171$. For each interval $[\lambda_{i-1}, \lambda_i]$ one needs to select an energy ϵ_i . We selected the midpoint of each interval to evaluate the corresponding

energy.

So, the HCLJ discrete version, with the midpoint selection, is given as:

$$\phi_{HCLJ}^{Dis}(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } x \leq 1 \\ 4\epsilon_{LJ} \left[\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0 + (2j-1)\frac{w}{2}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0 + (2j-1)\frac{w}{2}} \right)^6 \right] & \text{if } \lambda_0 + (j-1)w < x \leq \lambda_0 + jw \\ 0 & \text{if } x > \lambda_c. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The DPT expression for the reduced excess Helmholtz free-energy for a system of N particles interacting with a HCLJ potential in a volume V , at reduced temperature $T^* = \frac{kT}{\epsilon_{LJ}}$, and density $\rho^* = \rho\sigma_{LJ}^3$ can be expressed as: [36]

$$\begin{aligned} a^{ex}(\rho^*, T^*) &= a_{HS}(\rho^*) \\ &+ \frac{1}{T^*} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_1^S(\rho^*, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_1^S(\rho^*, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] \\ &+ \frac{1}{T^{*2}} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_2^S(\rho^*, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_2^S(\rho^*, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] \\ &+ \frac{1}{T^{*3}} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_3^S(\rho^*, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_3^S(\rho^*, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] \\ &+ \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\epsilon_j^* = \epsilon_j/\epsilon_{LJ}$, the a_i^S are the i -th free-energy perturbation terms of an S potential, where S denotes either a square-well (SW) ($\epsilon_j^* < 0$) or a square-shoulder (SS) ($\epsilon_j^* > 0$). Within this approach the following relation is assumed:

$$a_i^{SS}(\rho^*, \lambda_i, \epsilon_i^*) = (-1)^i a_i^{SW}(\rho^*, \lambda_i, \epsilon_i^*). \quad (6)$$

This assumption simplifies the evaluation of the Helmholtz free-energy since, as can be seen, Eq. (5) only requires the knowledge of $a_{HS}(\rho^*)$ and $a_i^{SW}(\rho^*, \lambda_{SW})$ terms.

Eq. (5) can be rewritten as:

$$a^{ex}(\rho^*, T^*) \equiv a_{HS}(\rho^*) + \frac{a_1(\rho^*)}{T^*} + \frac{a_2(\rho^*)}{T^{*2}} + \frac{a_3(\rho^*)}{T^{*3}} + \dots \quad (7)$$

Notice that in this expression the a_i terms are now only density dependent.

In this case we will also use the Carnahan-Starling equation of state [40] for the hard-sphere term. Since we need to know these expressions for all values of $1 < \lambda \leq \lambda_c$, for the SW perturbation terms: for ranges $1 < \lambda \leq 2.5$ we selected the Pavlyukhin[38] up to fourth-order a_i expressions. For $2.5 < \lambda \leq 3.0$ we used the first and second perturbation terms from Espindola *et al.*[41] and we set $a_3 = a_4 = 0$. For longer ranges, $\lambda > 3$, we

have chosen the analytic expressions given by Benavides and del Río[39] for the first and second-order terms and set $a_3 = a_4 = 0$.

C. Thermodynamic properties for SW and HCLJ potentials.

Having an analytical expression for the Helmholtz free-energy as a high temperature expansion allows one to obtain all thermodynamic properties as high temperature expansions. For instance, the compressibility factor, $Z = pV/Nk_B T = \rho^* \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial \rho^*} \right)_{T^*}$, and the internal energy, $u = \frac{U}{Nk_B T} = -T^* \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial T^*} \right)_{\rho^*}$, can also be expressed as high-temperature expansions:

$$Z(\rho^*, T^*) = z_{id} + z_{HS}(\rho^*) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z_n(\rho^*)}{T^{*n}} \quad (8)$$

and

$$u(\rho^*, T^*) = u_{id} + u_{HS}(\rho^*) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{u_n(\rho^*)}{T^{*n}}, \quad (9)$$

with $z_i = \rho^* \left(\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial \rho^*} \right)$ and $u_i = -T^* \left(\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial T^*} \right)$. The ideal compressibility factor and the ideal internal energy are denoted by z_{id} and u_{id} , respectively. Since in this case we are dealing with mono component fluids, $z_{id} = 1$ and $u_{id} = \frac{3}{2}$. The hard-sphere Carnahan-Starling compressibility factor is given as:

$$z_{HS} = \frac{1 + \eta + \eta^2 - \eta^3}{1 - \eta^3}, \quad (10)$$

and the Carnahan-Starling hard-sphere internal energy, u_{HS} , is zero. The reduced pressure can be computed by using:

$$p^* = \frac{p\sigma^3}{|\epsilon_{LJ}|} = Z\rho^*T^* \quad (11)$$

and the reduced chemical potential using:

$$\mu^* = \mu/k_B T = \frac{\partial(a\rho^*)}{\partial \rho^*} = a + Z. \quad (12)$$

One can obtain the vapour (ρ_g^*) and liquid (ρ_l^*) coexistence densities, by solving, for a given temperature, the conventional vapor–liquid equilibrium conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} p^*(\rho_l^*) &= p^*(\rho_g^*), \\ \mu^*(\rho_l^*) &= \mu^*(\rho_g^*), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

III. SUPERCRITICAL REGION

In order to determine the Widom line of the discrete potentials two methods were selected. The only input of these methods are their corresponding analytic EOS.

A. Thermodynamic curvature method

Riemannian geometry has been a successful frame of reference to determine first-order phase transitions, through the R-crossing method proposed by Ruppeiner *et al.*[15] Besides, they also used it to define the Widom line from another perspective, without the need of response functions information. The new definition is based on the relation $|R| \sim \xi^3$, with R being the Ricci curvature scalar, hereafter referred simply as curvature scalar. So, to obtain the Widom line, instead of estimating the maximum of ξ , which in general is difficult, one can estimate the maximum of R .

R is a measure of the geometric curvature of a given space, in which a metric tensor is defined. In the Riemannian geometry, the distance element, ds , among two points of the space can be measured defining a metric tensor, $ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu$, where x^μ and x^ν represent variables depending on the representation.

In the context of thermodynamics, the representation means a thermodynamic potential in terms of some thermodynamic variables.

A possible and useful representation, in which the metric tensor is diagonal, is the one associated to the Helmholtz free energy, $A(\rho, T)$. In this representation, when the thermodynamic variables are density and temperature, the metrics elements are:

$$g_{TT} = -\frac{1}{T} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial T^2}(\rho f) \quad (14)$$

$$g_{\rho\rho} = \frac{1}{T} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \rho^2}(\rho f), \quad (15)$$

where $f = \frac{A}{Nk_B}$ is the Helmholtz free energy per Boltzmann's constant and per particle. This energy is related to our reduced Helmholtz free energy, $a = A/Nk_B T$, as $f = Ta$.

The determinant g of the metric tensor is given by

$$g = g_{TT}g_{\rho\rho}. \quad (16)$$

The thermodynamic curvature scalar can be obtained in terms of the elements of the metric tensor, as:

$$R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial g_{\rho\rho}}{\partial T} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial g_{TT}}{\partial \rho} \right) \right]. \quad (17)$$

In this expression R has volume units. However, all our calculus were performed in reduced units and for this scalar we used $R^* = R/\sigma^3$.

B. Maxima of response functions method

The maxima of response functions method requires the knowledge of the locus of response functions. Since the thermodynamic properties of our EOS are given as functions of temperature and density, response functions will be expressed in terms of derivatives of these variables. Besides, they can be conveniently written in reduced units.

The response functions considered are:

- The thermal expansion coefficient:

$$\alpha_p = \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T} \right)_p, \quad (18)$$

which, in reduced units, can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_p^* = \frac{\epsilon \alpha_p}{k_B} = \frac{1}{\rho^*} \frac{\left(\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial T^*} \right)_{\rho^*}}{\left(\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial \rho^*} \right)_{T^*}}. \quad (19)$$

- The isochoric heat capacity,

$$c_V = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial T} \right)_V, \quad (20)$$

which, in reduced units can be expressed as:

$$c_V^* = \frac{c_V}{Nk_B} = 2T^* \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial T^*} \right)_{\rho^*} - T^{*2} \frac{\partial^2 a}{\partial T^{*2}}. \quad (21)$$

- The isothermal compressibility,

$$\beta_T = -\frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T} \right)_T, \quad (22)$$

which, in reduced units can be written as:

$$\beta_T^* = \frac{\epsilon \beta_T}{\sigma^3} = \frac{1}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial \rho^*} \right)_{T^*}^{-1}. \quad (23)$$

- The isobaric heat capacity,

$$c_p = \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \right)_p, \quad (24)$$

with H being the enthalpy. This response function in reduced units can be expressed as:

$$c_p^* = \frac{c_p}{Nk_B} = c_V^* + \frac{T^* \alpha_p^{*2}}{\rho^* \beta_T^*}. \quad (25)$$

As mentioned above, the main advantage of having an analytic equation of state for all cases considered is that all these response functions can be easily calculated.

IV. RESULTS

We present the analysis of the Widom lines in the temperature-pressure plane for the SW and HCLJ potentials. For both cases we determined the locus of the extrema of the response function and of the curvature scalar. The coincidence of all the lines requires a quantitative criterion since, as can be seen in most of the Widom line literature, such coincidence can be sensitive of the scale used for presenting the maxima location. So, in this work we have chosen the following quantitative criterion: In the $T^* - p^*$ plane, while moving away from the critical point, the Widom line will end when, at a fixed pressure, the distance in temperature corresponding to the locus of maxima of the pair of properties, which are more separated, is approximately 0.001. In this work, the more separated properties were always the thermal expansion coefficient and the isothermal compressibility:

$$\left| T_{\beta_{max}}^* - T_{C_{p_{max}}}^* \right| \sim 0.001. \quad (26)$$

Besides, as has been observed for many simple fluids, in the $\rho^* - p^*$ plane, the isotherms of the pressure in the subcritical vapor-liquid coexistence region present inflection points. These inflection points also appear for isotherms above the critical point. The thermodynamic states associated to these inflection points in the $T^* - p^*$ plane and their coincidence with the locus of the maxima response functions and curvature scalar will be investigated.

A. Square-well potential

For the SW potential we considered six ranges: $\lambda = 1.25, 1.5, 2.2, 5.0, 7.0,$ and 10.0 .

In Figure 1 the locus of maxima of the response functions, the negative of the scalar curvature, $-R^*$, and the inflection points, in the $T^* - p^*$ plane are presented for SW systems of intermediate and long ranges, respectively. The pressures and temperatures have been reduced with respect to the critical values. The critical values for these systems are given in Table I. As can be noticed from the figures it is not easy to distinguish where the Widom line ends. So, to look for the coincidence of the lines defined by the maxima of these functions we used the criterion described in equation (26). Widom's line details: coordinates of the end points, slopes (m_{WL}) and lengths (l_{SW}) for each SW range have been also included in Table I.

In order to find a relation between the Widom line ending point and the SW range, in Figure 2 we present the reduced ending temperature and pressure as a function

of λ . It can be noticed that reduced temperatures increase asymptotically as λ increases, reaching a limiting value for the longer ranges ($\lambda \geq 5.0$). The opposite occurs for reduced pressures; they decrease asymptotically reaching a limiting value for $\lambda \geq 3.0$. As can be seen, for intermediate ranges, the Widom line end point changes are pronounced; while, for long ranges, the Widom line shows a universal behavior.

By making a polynomial fit for these points we found:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{T^*}{T_c^*} \right)_{\text{end}} &= a_0 \lambda^{-a_1} + 1.018, \\ \left(\frac{P^*}{P_c^*} \right)_{\text{end}} &= b_0 \lambda^{-b_1} + 1.083, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where: $a_0 = -0.0096$, $a_1 = 2.1199$, $b_0 = 0.0280453$ and $b_1 = 6.25097$. This fit is shown as a continuous line in Figure 2.

We analyzed the vdW fluid applying the same criteria used in this work to obtain the Widom line and found that this line ends at $T^*/T_c^* = 1.020$ and $p^*/p_c^* = 1.082$. These values are close to the limiting ones obtained for long ranged SW fluids ($\lambda \geq 3.0$). For the vdW fluids, Brazhkin and Ryzhov[14] found that the Widom line ends at $T^*/T_c^* = 1.07$ and $p^*/p_c^* = 1.25$, while, in the work of May and Mausbach[21] the estimated values are $T^*/T_c^* = 1.05$ and $p^*/p_c^* = 1.20$ (see Figure 5d in that work). The differences in their predictions and ours could be due to the use of different criteria to determine the end of the Widom line. Besides, as mentioned previously, in the absence of a quantitative criterion, the coincidence of all the maxima lines can be sensitive to the scale used for presenting the maxima location; that is the case for these two works.

We conclude that the SW fluids of variable range have a Widom line in a noticeable region close to the critical point. Long-ranged SW fluids have a unique Widom line that looks almost like the vdW one.

Assuming that the Widom line is a line that connects the reduced critical point with the end point, in Figure 3 the slopes and lengths of the Widom lines are presented. For intermediate ranges the slopes and lengths decrease with the range, while for long ranges they remain constant. The only point that escapes from the monotonic behavior in the length of the Widom line is for $\lambda = 2.2$; we think that this behavior is caused by the use of the Pavlyukhin EOS that for this range, is close to its limit of applicability.

Figure 1. Locus of the maxima of the negative of the scalar curvature, $-R^*$, and some response functions: isobaric heat capacity, c_p^* , isobaric expansion coefficient, α_p^* , and isothermal compressibility, β_T^* , for a square well system with variable range, λ . The critical data for all systems are given in Table I. The coordinates of the end of the Widom line are shown as dotted lines. The inflection points, I_{T^*} , determined in the $\rho^* - p^*$ plane are also included.

Critical data				Widom line data			
λ	T_c^*	ρ_c^*	p_c^*	$\left(\frac{p^*}{p_c^*}\right)_{end}$	$\left(\frac{T^*}{T_c^*}\right)_{end}$	l_{WL}	m_{WL}
SW							
1.25	0.804	0.4114	0.1113	1.090	1.012	0.091	7.500
1.5	1.285	0.3102	0.1264	1.085	1.014	0.086	6.071
2.2	3.828	0.2687	0.3430	1.084	1.016	0.086	5.250
3.0	10.029	0.2497	0.9005	1.083	1.017	0.085	4.882
5.0	47.054	0.2505	4.2228	1.083	1.018	0.085	4.611
7.0	129.303	0.2497	11.5800	1.083	1.018	0.085	4.611
10.0	377.195	0.2494	33.7500	1.083	1.018	0.085	4.611
HCLJ							
	1.319	0.2750	0.1338	1.078	1.016	0.080	4.875

Table I. Widom line critical data, end points coordinates, slope (m_{WL}), and length (l_{WL}) for SW fluids of variable range and HCLJ system.

Figure 2. Coordinates of the Widom line ends as a function of the SW range.

B. Hard-Core Lennard-Jones

As a more general example of a discrete potential, we consider the HCLJ potential. In Table I, its critical data together with the Widom line information are presented. The critical data follows the trend of the critical data of the equation proposed by Thol *et al.*[42] ($\rho_c^* = 0.31$, $T_c^* = 1.32$, $p_c^* \sim 0.13$), which are in line with the average of critical simulation data reported in the literature. So, the critical point for the HCLJ and continuous LJ are similar. Due to this, we think that the Widom lines of both potential will occur in similar regions.

In Figure 5, we can see that the coincidence of the maxima of the response functions, the absolute value of the curvature scalar, and the inflection points, using our quantitative criterion, occurs in the region delimited by $T^*/T_c^* = 1.016$ and $p^*/p_c^* = 1.078$ and shown as dashed

Figure 3. Slope and length of the SW Widom lines as a function of the range.

Figure 4. Vapour-liquid coexistence curve (blue dotted line) and Widom line (magenta continuous line) in the T^*-p^* plane for the SW potentials considered in this work. The Widom line looks like a continuation of the vapour-liquid coexistence curve for all cases.

lines. This region is contained in the region proposed by Brazhkin and Ryzhov,[14] delimited by $T^*/T_c^* = 1.1$ and $p^*/p_c^* = 1.5$, for the continuous LJ potential. The differences may be due to the criterion to estimate the end of the Widom line and that one is a hard-core LJ and the latter is the continuous original LJ.

C. General Remarks

For all discrete potentials considered in this work, we have included in all figures the corresponding coordinates of the pressure inflection points, I_T , determined in the $\rho^* - p^*$ plane. As can be seen, these points also coincide with the rest of the properties in the Widom line region in the $T^* - p^*$ plane. *It seems that the locus of the pressure*

inflection points near the critical point can be considered as an alternative and simple criterion to determine the Widom line. The main advantage of this criterion is that inflection points are easier to obtain than the extrema of response functions and/or scalar curvature. However, we need an additional condition to determine the end of this line; this condition could be the coincidence of the locus of these inflection points and the maxima of the isothermal compressibility in the $T^* - p^*$ plane. We suggest to consider the isothermal compressibility, since the maxima of this property deviate earlier than the rest of the extrema of the response properties and the curvature scalar, at least for all the cases considered in this work.

Additionally, in Figure 4 and Figure 6 we present the vapor-liquid coexistence curve in the $T^* - p^*$ plane and the Widom lines for each of the systems considered in this work. It can be seen that the Widom line looks like an extension of the vapor-liquid coexistence curve in this plane, as was earlier proposed by Jones and Walker.[2]

Figure 5. Locus of the maxima of the negative of the scalar curvature, $-R^*$ and some response functions: isobaric heat capacity c_p^* , isobaric expansion coefficient, α_p^* , isothermal compressibility, β_T^* , for a Hard-Core Lennard-Jones system. The inflection points, I_{T^*} , obtained in a $\rho^* - p^*$ plane are also included.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, using analytical equations of state, the Widom lines for a family of Square-Well and for a Hard-Core Lennard-Jones potentials were obtained. To determine these lines we selected the temperature-pressure plane to look for the coincidence of the locus of extrema of isobaric heat capacity, isothermal compressibility, thermal expansion coefficient, and curvature scalar. Besides, a quantitative criterion to determine the end of these Widom lines was proposed.

Figure 6. Widom line as a continuation of the Vapor-Liquid coexistence curve in the T^*-p^* plane for a Hard-Core Lennard-Jones System.

The effect of varying the square-well range on the Widom lines, was studied. For intermediate ranges it was found that, when reducing thermodynamic quantities with respect to the critical values, the end line temperature increases monotonically with the SW range ($\lambda \leq 3.0$), reaching a constant value for longer ranges. Concerning the reduced pressures of the end lines, for intermediate ranges, they decrease monotonically, reaching a constant value for longer ranges. The asymptotic values of these end line coordinates resemble those of a van der Waals fluid.

The Widom line for the Hard-Core Lennard-Jones potential was obtained using the Discrete Perturbation Theory which provides analytical equations of state for different discrete potentials. Since the critical data of this discrete version of a Lennard-Jones are similar to its continuous version, one could expect that the the Widom lines predicted for both potentials would be very close. So, the estimated Widom line should follow the same trends followed by the Lennard-Jones line. This result shows the advantage of having analytical equations of state to study the supercritical region and also that the Discrete Perturbation Theory is a useful tool.

We propose a simple criterion to determine the Widom line, based on the determination of the inflection points of pressure as a function of density in the supercritical region. In the temperature-pressure plane, the coincidence of the locus of these inflection points and the locus of the maximum of the isothermal compressibility determine the Widom line.

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